

Economics and Management Law

Description

This project created a set of linked datasets that describe changes in legal code to company, insolvency and labour law over time. The datasets use unique 'leximetric' coding to estimate the effects of legal reforms to shareholder, creditor and worker rights. The project was first made public in 2009 and a new, updated set of information is to be published in June 2016. Organisations such as the International Labour Organisation (ILO) and Asian Development Bank have already used the datasets to conduct their own research and the World Bank has used the coding methodology to improve its own data collection methods.

Benefits

Data collection and re-use has a number of benefits including the econometric analysis by other research teams, use of the unique coding algorithm to produce more data that covers additional countries and years, and the citation of the original data in multiple academic publications.

Understanding the changing nature of jobs in national and international contexts enables policy makers and international organisations like the ILO to respond to real-time economic conditions and job availability.

For example, research by the ILO published in 2015 suggests that employment insecurity is increasing as workers are offered more informal, short-term contracts, which may result in increasing levels of poverty. This knowledge can be translated into local, regional and national policies designed to support the economic impact of the changing nature of work and paid labour.

Supporting links

<http://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/full/10.1086/674106>

Accessed 10 June 2016.

<http://asq.sagepub.com/content/61/1/125.abstract>

Accessed 10 June 2016.

http://ji.sc/The_Changing_Nature_Of_Jobs

Accessed 10 June 2016.